

Psychological Landscape of Consumption: Examining the Nexus between Self-Esteem, Dunning Kruger Effect and Conspicuous Consumption for Gen Z

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Abstract

Consumption is an essential tool for an individual to express themselves in society. One crucial consumption pattern to consider in this situation is conspicuous consumption. It is possible to discuss numerous psychographic factors that influence an individual's consumption behavior. In this context, individuals may use consumption as a tool to bridge the gap between their ideal and real selves, thereby building self-esteem. Based on this conceptual framework and the current literature, conspicuous consumption behavior may be a choice an individual can make to increase self-esteem. This study examines the moderator role of the Dunning-Kruger (D-K) Effect in the interaction of self-esteem and conspicuous consumption. Considering the variables, the research is interdisciplinary, drawing on the literature in psychology, microeconomics, and consumer behavior. The research examines how the interaction between the dependent and independent variables emerges in the moderation of the D-K Effect, a self-assessment failure, within the Gen Z population. Finally, the analysis found that a high level of D-K moderates the effect of self-esteem on conspicuous consumption.

Keywords: Dunning-Kruger Effect, Conspicuous Consumption, Self-Esteem, Consumer Behavior

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1. Introduction

The consumer behavior discipline has its roots in microeconomics. In addition, the individual's consumption behavior is shaped by many internal and external factors. One of them is psychological, such as “*Self-Esteem*.” This study aims to examine whether the “*Dunning-Kruger Effect*” and “*Self-Esteem*” are statistically significant in explaining an individual's “*Conspicuous Consumption*” tendency. From this perspective, this study examines the effects of Gen Z's D-K and self-esteem levels on conspicuous consumption tendencies through their

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clothing consumption habits. That is because clothing consumption behavior is considered a significant indicator of conspicuous consumption in the literature (Das & Indibara, 2025; O’Cass & McEwen, 2004; Segal & Podoshen, 2013).

Conspicuous consumption generally refers to the conscious spending of an individual's limited economic resources on luxury goods that have symbolic value and features that can be noticed by others (Chaudhuri & Majumdar, 2010). The underlying reason for this behavior is said to be the desire to prove one's wealth and power to others (Perez-Truglia, 2013, p. 146). On the other hand, self-esteem is a concept related to how an individual evaluates themselves within the framework of their own expectations and the expectations of others (Mocanu & Spanache, 2021, p. 46). In other words, it is an individual's self-assessment of their self-worth (Consiglio & van Osselaer, 2022, p. 1). An individual's level of self-esteem is said to influence their propensity to consume luxury goods with conspicuous value (Khan et al., 2024, p. 2). On the other hand, the Dunning-Kruger effect is generally considered a metacognitive bias and can be defined as an individual's tendency to overestimate their problem-solving abilities or competencies in any given subject (Bradley et al., 2022; Uko et al., 2024). Furthermore, Generation Z is the youngest of the current generations and is distinguished by differences in their consumption behaviors. It is stated that Generation Z constructs their identity through consumption not only in the physical world but also in the digital world (Djafarova & Bowes, 2021).

No study in the literature examines “*Conspicuous Consumption*,” “*Self-Esteem*,” and the “*Dunning-Kruger Effect*” together. However, there are binary combinations of them. For example, studies such as “*Dunning-Kruger and Consumer Behavior*” (Nam, 2021), “*Dunning-Kruger and Self-Esteem*” (Christopher et al., 2023), and “*Consumer Behavior and Self-Esteem*” (Stuppy et al., 2020) can be found in the literature. Notably, researchers from diverse disciplines conduct these studies, suggesting that the subject has a multidisciplinary dimension. The most striking aspect of the research is its revelation of the role of cognitive self-evaluation deficiencies in the emergence of conspicuous consumer behavior as a compensatory behavior for low self-esteem. Therefore, this study will bridge cognitive psychology and marketing by examining selected determinants of consumer behavior. Furthermore, this research offers useful information for marketing practitioners regarding segmentation, communication messages, and methodology.

After a rigorous literature review of “*Conspicuous Consumption*,” “*Self-Esteem*,” and “*Dunning-Kruger Effect*” in the research, a method based on statistical principles was developed. The research model has been tested using SPSS and AMOS, and suggestions have been made to practitioners and researchers based on the results. Thus, it aims to fill a gap in the literature and to provide useful information for marketing practitioners on the consumption behavior of young consumer groups.

2. Literature Review

The tendency of individuals to evaluate themselves more positively than others has been a topic of discussion in social psychology for many years. That is called the better-than-average effect. With the work of Kruger and Dunning (2011; 2003; 1999; 2013), it gained popularity and became known as the Dunning-Kruger effect. According to the Dunning-Kruger effect, people who are generally inadequate in a particular subject are unaware of their deficiencies. According to the Dunning-Kruger effect, most people who exaggerate their competencies in this type are individuals with low competencies (Dunning, 2011; Kruger & Dunning, 1999). Even to be able to define a disability, competence is required (Dunning et al., 2003; Kruger & Dunning, 1999). Kruger and Dunning (1999) argue that individuals with low proficiency levels cannot perceive their inadequacies due to weak metacognition, meta-memory, metacognition, and self-assessment levels. Unlike individuals with low competency, those with high competency perceive their competency as lower than it actually is (Kruger & Dunning, 1999). Therefore, the outcomes for competent and incompetent individuals in competency-based self-assessment are the opposite. Regarding the Dunning-Kruger effect, research has been conducted across different academic disciplines. For example, there is evidence that students in higher education overestimate the competence levels of physicians and salespeople (Mahmood, 2016). In addition, studies show that individuals hold opinions without knowing their attitudes, such as opposition to compulsory vaccination (Motta et al., 2018) or partisan tendencies (Anson, 2018). On the other hand, Zell and Krizan (2014) assert a correlation between the self-assessment score and the objective competence level. When the consumer behavior literature on the Dunning-Kruger effect is examined, it is evident that numerous studies have been conducted on this topic. For example, betting on sports competitions (Bulboacă & Țierean, 2021), consumer empowerment (Nam, 2021), the tendency towards alternative medicine (Shaffer, 2022), and seeking financial advice (Meyer et al., 2018) are some consumer behavior research subjects in the literature. On the other hand, it is said that individuals with a high Dunning-Kruger level cannot accurately evaluate the qualities of products and services (Balážiková, 2018). Aqueveque (2018) also states that consumers with high D-K levels can have difficulty evaluating product quality. Therefore, the meanings attributed to conspicuous products, as well as the post-consumption evaluations of people with high D-K levels, are also contradictory. Another critical issue is that consumers with high D-K levels seek low-level information in their purchasing processes (Trotta, 2021). Consumers whose self-confidence has increased due to the D-K effect risk wasting their financial resources by making purchases with insufficient information. The results of Balasubramnian and Sargent's (2020) study on financial products also support this assessment. In the study, the D-K effect is called the "blind spot," an illusion due to a negative level of competence. It is said that individuals with high D-K levels are likely to misallocate their capital by purchasing these products, as they may misjudge the financial products (Balasubramnian & Sargent, 2020).

Self-esteem, on the other hand, is an individual's self-assessment and can fluctuate between positive and negative levels at different times (Bailey, 2003; Leary, 1999). In particular, how the symbolic value of the products the individual consumes in reaching the ideal self is perceived by others is an essential reference point for self-assessment. For this reason, it can be said that there is a significant relationship between self-esteem and the individual's conspicuous consumption behavior. It is also said that individuals turn to compensatory consumption behavior when they perceive a risk that could lower their self-esteem (Koles et al., 2018, p. 109). Therefore, conspicuous consumption behaviors in this context can be considered a precautionary or buffering behavior. Self-esteem is generally defined as the extent to which an individual believes he or she has socially desirable qualities, such as competence, being liked by others, and physical attractiveness (Leary, 1999). According to another definition, self-esteem summarizes everything positive and negative about which an individual evaluates and forms an opinion (Bailey, 2003). As a result, it is possible to observe a high level of self-esteem if the individual's self-assessment is positive, and a low level of self-esteem if it is negative. Low self-esteem may be associated with various personal and psychological problems, such as low academic achievement, substance abuse, and depression (Leary, 1999). Sheldon et al. (2001) define self-esteem as a basic need that can be confused with the individual's goals. Therefore, it is a unique marketing and consumer research concept, driven by a need. Some studies in the consumer behavior literature examine the relationship between self-esteem and consumption. These studies indicate that low self-esteem may lead to negative behaviors, such as compulsive buying (Baltacı & Eser, 2022) or excessive food consumption (French et al., 1995). On the other hand, some studies report that individuals increase their self-esteem by building their assets (Truong & McColl, 2011). Besides, although it is known that some consumption behaviors have short-term restorative effects on an individual's self-esteem, these effects are expected to fade unless the factors that cause low self-esteem are eliminated (Mandel et al., 2021). In other words, consumption is a purposeful behavior that can sometimes increase an individual's self-esteem. The D-K effect is said to involve individuals convincing themselves that their performance is better than others, thereby reinforcing their self-image and ego (Bunay et al., 2018, p. 386). Within this fragile structure, individuals may transform consumer behavior into a tool for self-affirmation, using it to produce tangible evidence of the high performance they believe they possess. In other words, products with symbolic value that signal prestige to the outside world can become attractive to these individuals, leading to conspicuous consumer behavior because the symbolic value of a product is actually measured not by the individual themselves, but by the value given to it by other individuals who see it being used and who do not own it (Sahin & Nasir, 2022, p. 73).

The final concept in this research is conspicuous consumption. The concept of conspicuous consumption was first defined by Thorstein Veblen in 1899. Veblen (1899) describes conspicuous consumption as an action an individual performs consciously to raise his status. Furthermore, Veblen (1899) stated that this action was also a waste of time and resources. When the consumer behavior literature is examined, it is seen that the subject is generally approached along the axes of Signal

Theory, evolutionary psychology, and Cultural Theory. According to the Signal Theory, conspicuous consumption is a signaling behavior in which an individual acquires goods to influence others (Lee & Shrum, 2012). Products are the things consumers use to reflect their identities and increase their social visibility, as they carry symbolic meanings (Chaudhuri & Majumdar, 2010). For example, Nelissen and Meijers (2011, p. 353) suggest that some consumers prefer the brand logo to be visible on the luxury products they use. It is argued that this is done to enhance their perceived status in comparison to others. From this perspective, conspicuous consumption can be considered an economic and psychological act (Ryu, 2015). Another study suggests that conspicuous consumption can serve as a signaling device to attract the opposite sex (Griskevicius et al., 2007, p. 99). Therefore, it can be said that conspicuous consumer behavior has evolutionary foundations. On the other hand, evolutionary psychology is another approach that tries to explain conspicuous consumption behavior. Evolutionary psychology researchers claim that conspicuous consumption behavior is more common among men because women prefer men with high status or those likely to achieve it (Koliotofis, 2022). On the other hand, one element that can evolve is social culture. It is said that conspicuous consumption behavior also differs between cultures (Bellezza et al., 2017). Social cultural capital is a set of distinctive tastes, preferences, skills, knowledge, and actions (Holt, 1998). These components guide consumers about what they can and cannot consume and what cultural meanings they can ascribe to symbols. Finally, conspicuous consumption is an economic behavior that individuals consciously engage in and that has material and moral consequences. In addition, it is understood that it can vary according to demographic variables, such as gender, and sociological variables, such as culture. Studies in the literature suggest that conspicuous consumption is also a compensatory behavior (Wang et al., 2022, p. 522). Compensatory consumption is a method individuals resort to in order to eliminate feelings of insecurity arising from psychological deficiencies and inadequacies experienced for various reasons (Hammad & El-Bassiouny, 2024, p. 658). Considering this information, it can be assumed that individuals with a high D-K effect may attempt to compensate for the gap between their true and ideal selves through conspicuous consumption, as they perceive themselves as more than they actually are. Thus, these individuals may try to validate their inflated yet flawed self-evaluations by using high-status, symbolically valuable products. However, it must be noted that the amount of interdisciplinary research on the D-K Effect in the literature remains insufficient.

One-point worth noting is that the relationship between self-esteem and conspicuous consumption is controversial in the literature. For example, Lewis and Moital (2016, p. 151) attribute low conspicuous consumption to low self-esteem. However, Tenia et al. (2022, p. 55) argue that high conspicuous consumption behavior, particularly in Generation Z, is driven by low self-esteem and a desire for acceptance within social groups. As the literature indicates, conspicuous consumption is complex and dynamic, influenced by numerous factors. In this context, this study examines the effects of academic D-K and self-esteem on conspicuous consumption behavior among Generation Z.

3. Methodology

Research Model and Hypotheses

In the literature, one of the essential products consumers prefer to display conspicuous consumption behavior with is clothing (O’Cass & McEwen, 2004). It is stated that the reason for this is the association of such products with hedonic consumption and the prestige they carry (Avcı, 2021). In addition, it is stated that the symbolic meanings of clothing, in terms of gender discrimination across cultures and in conveying the power and status of the individual, affect conspicuous consumption (Segal & Podoshen, 2013). Therefore, it can be said that the individual's clothing preferences are related to both self-esteem and conspicuous consumption behavior. For this reason, in the study, clothing products were preferred for evaluating participants' conspicuous consumption tendencies.

The signals that an individual sends about his/her social identity can show how he/she sees himself/herself, which group he/she feels, his/her cultural identity, or how he/she wants to be seen by others (Tajfel & Turner, 2004; Willer et al., 1989). The symbols preferred by the individual in signals conveyed through consumption indicate the level of conspicuous consumption and provide clues about the ideal self the individual seeks to achieve. From this point of view, the first hypothesis of the research was formed.

H₁: Self-esteem level has a statistically significant effect on conspicuous consumption behavior.

To determine the D-K Effect, the difference between participants' perceived and actual academic success levels was considered. The most important reason is the inverse relationship between academic achievement and self-esteem in the literature (Leary, 1999).

H₂: The D-K effect has a statistically significant moderator effect between self-esteem and conspicuous consumption behavior.

To determine the level of the D-K Effect, participants were asked, “How do you see your academic success level?” and were asked to rate on a 4-point Likert scale from “Very Bad-Very Good” to “Very Good.” Then, the “What is your current cumulative grade point out of 4?” question was asked. The points shared by the participants in the quadrant system were then multiplied by 25 and converted into the hundredth system. Finally, analyses of the D-K Effect were conducted, assuming that the negative difference between these two points reflected a difference between competence and perceived competence.

This study aims to empirically examine the relationship between the deviations in Gen Z’s self-assessment levels (D-K Effect) regarding their current academic achievement, self-esteem, and conspicuous consumption. The main

question of the research is, “Do self-esteem and Dunning-Kruger effect level have an effect on conspicuous consumption behavior?”

The research model is shown in Figure1.

Figure 1. Research model

Source: Author’s own creation

Participants

The literature offers different estimates of when Gen Z will start, depending on when those born are. In the literature, there is a wide range of birth-year estimates for Gen Z, from 1993 to 1997, in articles with 100 or more citations. Some of these articles are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. The beginning of the birth year of Gen Z, according to different research

Author	The Beginning of the Birth Year for Gen Z
Turner (2015)	1993
Cilliers (2017)	1995
Jiří (2016)	1996
Marshall & Wolanskyj-Spinner (2020)	1997

Source: Author’s own creation

Some distinguishing features set Generation Z apart. These features can be broadly listed as follows:

- Compared to other generations, they are less prone to voting or belonging to various groups,
- They are optimistic about the future,
- Their problem-solving skills are low,
- Their individuality and selfishness levels are high,
- Social networks are essential to their lives, and technology is a part of their identity (Singh & Dangmei, 2016).

It is evident that studies conducted in Turkey are similar to global studies on the starting year or characteristic features of Gen Z. Therefore, to ensure that all participants are from Gen Z, the population was defined as Turkish university

students or graduates born in 1997 or later. According to the data of the Turkish Statistical Institute (2022), the population of the Z generation in Turkey cannot be less than 18,735,111. In addition, according to data from the Turkish Higher Education Institution (2023), 6,401,149 students were registered at the undergraduate and associate degree levels in Turkey during the 2022-2023 academic year. Although the population's boundaries cannot be clearly drawn, it is understood that the number exceeds one million. Karagöz (Karagöz, 2019, p. 308) states that valid data should be collected from at least 384 individuals in populations of one million or more at a significance level of 0.05. For this reason, this limit was determined as the minimum sample size. The data were collected in the digital environment using convenience sampling via Google Forms.

Measures

To measure “*Conspicuous Consumption*” in the study, Phillips and Back's (2011) scale, consisting of 17 items and with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.93, was condensed and used. In addition, the Rosenberg (1965) scale with ten items and a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.76 was used to measure the “*Self-Esteem*”. Although Turkish adaptations of the scales exist, it was decided that further adaptation would be appropriate due to their use in a specific sample. For this reason, “*Face Validity*” was established by considering the opinions of three experts with academic translation competence in the subject. Subsequently, a preliminary test was conducted to assess the scales' usability. Data were collected using a formula developed by the researcher to measure the D-K Effect. This study examined the difference between perceived and actual academic success levels to identify participants with D-K tendencies. In order for a participant to be considered in the D-K category, the following condition must be met:

$$\text{Actual Academic Success (\%)} - \text{Perceived Academic Success (\%)} < 0$$

As the formula indicates, the Dunning-Kruger Effect is analyzed as a categorical variable in this study. Pre-tests were conducted, with data collected from 90 people who met the sample selection criteria.

Procedure

This research was carried out in accordance with ethical principles within the framework of the “*Turkish Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive*” and the “*Helsinki Declaration*”.

Data were collected via Google Forms between 5 May 2023 and 15 June 2023. At the beginning of the form, an informed consent form was presented to the participants, and their consent to voluntary participation was obtained. In addition, participants were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time. The invitation to participate in the research was announced on social media, the student alumni system, and various digital platforms.

Statistics

To determine whether the data are suitable for parametric analysis, the Kurtosis-Skewness values were first checked. Then, frequency analysis, reliability analysis, and exploratory factor analysis were performed using SPSS to analyze the research data. In addition, the model's structural analysis was conducted using path analysis in AMOS.

4. Findings

Analyses were carried out on the 532 forms that met the formula condition and the inclusion criteria. The values obtained from the Skewness-Kurtosis analysis ranged from -1,225 to +1,139 for the self-esteem scale and from -1,233 to +1,259 for the conspicuous consumption scale. Tabachnick and Fidell (2013) state that if the Skewness-Kurtosis values are between -1.5 and +1.5, the data can be analyzed with parametric tests. Based on this information, parametric tests were used in the analysis.

It was determined that the D-K scores of these participants ranged from 0,5 to 40. A four-level categorization of D-K values was used to apply statistical tests. Each D-K level and the number of participants for each level are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Categories for the D-K Effect

Range	Level	Number of Participants in the Category
0,01-10,00	Very Low (a)	233
10,01-20,00	Low (b)	137
20,01-30,00	High (c)	94
30,01-40,00	Very High (d)	68
Total (N)		532

Source: Author's own creation

After determining the D-K levels, factor analysis was performed to examine how the self-esteem and conspicuous consumption scales performed in a sample exhibiting D-K characteristics. As a result of the analysis, two items that load more than one factor in both scales were deleted. The summary table of the obtained question sets is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Factor and reliability analysis results for self-esteem and conspicuous consumption scales

Scale	Items	Dimension	Tot. Var. Exp.	Cr. Alpha
Self Esteem	8	1	66,12	0,711
Conspicuous Consumption	15	3	73,49	0,942

Source: Author's calculations

After the scales were examined, the model was tested. First, it was examined whether self-esteem affects conspicuous consumption in the model without a moderator variable. Using AMOS, a path analysis tested the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Figure 2. Testing of the model without moderator variable

Source: Author’s calculations

According to that test, it is understood that self-esteem does not significantly affect conspicuous consumption behavior for this sample.

Table 4. Testing of the model without moderator variable

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
CCD-1	<---	Self-Esteem	-0,18	0,429	-0,419	0,675
CCD-2	<---	Self-Esteem	0,079	0,487	0,162	0,871
CCD-3	<---	Self-Esteem	0,433	0,405	1,069	0,285

Source: Author’s calculations

The D-K effect was added to the model as a moderator variable in the second stage, and the test was repeated.

Figure 3. Testing of the model with moderator variable
Source: Author’s calculations

The repeated test showed that the model did not yield a statistically significant result at three of the four levels of the D-K effect. However, the model became statistically significant for the High D-K group.

Table 5. Testing of the model with moderator variable

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
CCD-3	<---	Self-Esteem	2,166	0,808	2,682	0,007	c
CCD-2	<---	Self-Esteem	2,166	0,808	2,682	0,007	c
CCD-1	<---	Self-Esteem	2,166	0,808	2,682	0,007	c

Source: Author’s calculations

As a result, the analysis shows that the Dunning-Kruger level plays a moderating role in the effect of self-esteem on conspicuous consumption behavior.

5. Conclusions

The most important finding of the study is that conspicuous consumption behavior is found among certain groups who think their academic competence is higher than it actually is. Although no study in the literature directly makes this inference, past research suggests that such a situation may exist. For example, the literature states that people who misjudge their competence can make poor decisions (Ames & Kammrath, 2004; Kruger & Dunning, 1999). On the other hand, people with low self-esteem tend to prefer products with high material value to gain approval from their social circles (Richins, 1994). This study establishes the missing link in the literature with this critical finding. Additionally, although the study did not reveal a significant relationship between self-esteem and conspicuous

consumption, it can be argued that this consumption behavior serves as an adaptive mechanism for individuals with high D-K levels, given their inflated self-esteem regarding academic achievement.

On the other hand, the research has other contributions to the literature. “*Conspicuous Consumption Behavior*” and “*Dunning-Kruger Syndrome*” have attracted significant attention since their introduction to the literature. However, the literature shows that the number of studies empirically using the D-K Effect to explain consumer behavior is almost nonexistent. This study provides empirical evidence on how the D-K effect serves as a psychological motivator of conspicuous consumption behavior. Based on this, this research is a critical step in developing an innovative approach. The model tested in the research and its use for practitioners and researchers are explained in this section.

First, the D-K Syndrome detection method based on the difference between perceived and actual academic success used in the research provides reliable data for detecting a concrete self-evaluation deficiency. Therefore, it provides a basis for future research on various variables related to competence-based self-evaluation in academia. On the other hand, a similar approach can be used for perceived and actual competence levels of other competencies. In addition, as shown in the referenced model, when the D-K Syndrome level is added as a moderator variable, the model, which is not statistically significant under normal conditions, may become significant. Therefore, it can be inferred that there are implicit relationships among various dependent and independent variables in samples of people with D-K Syndrome across various populations. For this reason, adding D-K Syndrome to the research model as a moderator in future studies may help determine these relationships.

Given that consumption is a tool individual use to reach the ideal self, the results of this research may yield two distinct outcomes for practitioners. The first critical takeaway from this study for marketing executives is that brands targeting consumers with high D-K levels should prioritize status signaling. That is because these consumers may choose status-enhancing products to confirm or prove their high level of competence. Therefore, products reflecting an image of expertise, high status, or success can be designed for this audience. The second is to be aware of the D-K effect in professional support for individuals with problematic consumption behaviors, such as impulsive and compulsive buying, especially those who cannot exercise adequate control over their consumption. It is helpful to inform people in this situation that consumption patterns are not a way to prove academic achievement, and that uncontrolled shopping can lead to financial and social problems. Furthermore, the difference between an individual's actual level of achievement and their perceived achievement can be indicative of other or broader self-assessment issues. Therefore, guidance units within institutions can establish preventative feedback mechanisms. That can prevent individuals from becoming victims of consumer behavior stemming from errors in self-assessment. Individuals may need to know the difference between their expected and actual academic achievements. Apart from its effect on purchasing behavior, this difference may

also be related to other problematic behaviors. Therefore, it may be beneficial for school guidance and counseling departments to collect student feedback at certain points and work to reduce the gap between these two.

Limitations and Future Directions

Academic achievement was used to determine the level of Dunning-Kruger Syndrome in the study. However, this syndrome may also occur for different competencies. Therefore, the term Dunning-Kruger Syndrome used in this study is generally used as Academic Dunning-Kruger Syndrome.

Another limitation is that the research participants are Generation Z Turkish youth. The literature contains studies showing cultural differences in “Conspicuous Consumption” behavior. For this reason, the research results may differ across samples selected from different cultures.

The method proposed in this study can be used in future studies to test the D-K Effect on academic competence over various variables. In addition, a broader range of outputs can be produced to explain conspicuous consumption behavior by replacing the independent variable with different psychographic variables, such as self, personality, and values, in the research model, or by adding them as independent variables to the model.

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